

THE KINDERGARTENERS' MONTHLY PROGRESS IN ALPABASA READING PROGRAM AND THE MONITORING TOOL RESULT

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The Kindergarteners' Monthly Progress in Alpabasa Reading Program and the Monitoring Tool Result

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Abstract

This study made use a descriptive research approach for it wanted to determine the findings of the learners' checklist. The results of the monitoring instrument utilized by the respondents' parents or guardians, as well as the teacher-actual researcher's monitoring, were subjected to a descriptive analysis. Parents and teachers used a monitoring tool as a result of this. This study used an intervention program to track the respondents' development in terms of letter recognition and reading CVC patterns. As a result, the parents and teacher focused on the result of both monitoring tools. This study adapted the alpabasa learning sets and alpabasa instructional cards of the Department of Education. These materials were carefully considered as a basis to the existing game-based program by integrating more multi-sensory learning approaches in reading. Conclusions were derived from the results that the monitoring tools used by the parent and the teacher and the result of the diagnostic test administered to the respondents were proven to be effective for the results of both the diagnostic test and the monitoring tool result have remarkable difference. Also, it improved the reading performance of the respondents.

Keywords: *alpabasa instructional card, alpabasa learning sets, diagnostic test, descriptive research, intervention program*

Introduction

Pre-schoolers can learn a lot from educational television, but toddlers may learn more from interactive digital media such as video clips, touchscreen mobile applications, television and videos alone, which do not require them to interact. The specific conditions that lead to learning from media are unclear when there is no supervision from the parents and teachers. Not all types of interactive media increase learning and not all children learn to the same degree from these videos. But thankfully, there are reading programs that use media as their source of instruction. These are play-based programs that allow the learners to play while learning.

Kindergarteners are small sponges that learn what is taught to them. If they are taught to read in two languages simultaneously, they will learn. It was in 2011 that Alpabasa was born. Alpabasa's first material was a 31-page book that turned in Filipino flashcards focusing on syllabication. With support from Sa Aklat Sisikat, this first Alpabasa material was shared with over 100 public school teachers. The vision of the Alpabasa Reading Program is to make every Filipino child a reader.

The Alpabasa Reading Program has online educational videos that help children learn how to read. According to Pabiton (2015) "Changing lives one syllable at a time" is one of their goals. Regardless of age, when you teach someone to read you truly change their lives and turn on their passion for success. The first stage of the program is an assessment of children's literacy skills and any less determined person would have been discouraged.

Learners today are using educational videos and educational games as tools for learning everything from basic skills. It is important to provide tools to help them process the information and monitor their understanding cited by Brame (2015). Using video clips to convey appropriate and complementary information has been shown to increase learners' retention and ability to transfer information and increase student engagement with videos. Abstract topics that once seemed difficult to teach and learn are now more accessible and understandable thanks to the availability of educational videos for online learning.

The researcher observed that the children were in such need of their teacher but they are equipped enough to meet the needs of their learners due to the health protocols imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic. This reading program is implemented through limited face-to-face instruction to the identified struggling readers with the stringent observance of health protocols.

Relatively, the researcher has permission from the health officers and barangay officials for proper assistance. This study attempted to know if the Alpabasa Reading Program would be effective in kindergarteners and help them easily learn how to read. This is an intervention to existing programs in the department. This reading program lasted for eighteen (18) days.

Research Questions

The study ascertained the influence on reading skills among kindergarten learners in Baloi Central Elementary School. The researcher was required to answer the following questions:

1. What are the monthly progresses of the kindergarteners in Alpabasa Reading Program in terms of:
 - 1.1. video clips/ music; and
 - 1.2. provided checklist?
2. What are the Alpabasa Monitoring Tool results conducted by the parents?

3. What are the Alfabasa monitoring tool results?
4. Is there a significant difference between the monthly progress of the kindergarteners in Alfabasa Reading Program and the monitoring tool result conducted by parents?
5. Is there a significant difference between the monthly progress of the kindergarteners in Alfabasa reading program and the monitoring tool result conducted by parents based on their pretest assessment?
6. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest monthly progress of the kindergarteners as conducted by parents?
7. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest monthly progress of the kindergarteners as conducted by teachers?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive analysis characterizes the world or a phenomenon answering questions about who, what, where, when, and to what extent. Whether the goal is to identify and describe trends and variation in populations, create new measures of key phenomena, or describe samples in studies aimed at identifying causal effects, description plays a critical role in the scientific process in general and education research in particular.

Descriptive analysis stands on its own as a research product, such as when it identifies socially important phenomena that have not previously been recognized. In many instances, the description can also point toward causal understanding and to the mechanisms behind causal relationships.

This study employed a descriptive research design for it would only focus on determining the results of the checklist of the learners. A descriptive analysis was used on the result of the monitoring tool conducted by the parent or guardian of the respondents and the actual monitoring of the teacher-researcher.

Respondents

The respondents were the kindergarteners of Baloi Central Elementary School, Baloi West District, Division of Lanao del Norte. Determining the respondents of the study was based in the school's reading inventory report. Home visitations were also employed upon the monitoring of the reading program. The monitoring procedure was based on the parent's assessment and teacher's assessment. These tools were used in the descriptive analysis of the study. This determined if the play-based learning instruction through remedial reading is effective that would lead to a much brighter and broader perspective of innovating to help learners achieve their best potentials.

Instrument

This study adapted the alfabasa learning sets and alfabasa instructional cards of the Department of Education. These materials were carefully considered as a basis to the existing game-based program by integrating more multi-sensory learning approaches in reading. The alfabasa reading program is founded by Filipino innovation, it is a play-based program in teaching reading that aims to effectively teach kinder school children how to read in a given time Pabiton (2015). The monitoring tool used reading material, diagnostic tools and tracking device to gather the data. Some modifications were made to cater the respondents' literacy level.

Procedure

In the gathering of data, the researcher asked the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct this study. This was followed by the researcher's intent to the District Supervisor and School Principal for their approval to conduct a study. Letters to the respondents duly signed by the Dean of the Graduate School were also observed.

With the stringent health protocols imposed due to COVID-19 pandemic, data was gathered through home visitation with the adherence to health protocols. Learners' profiling was made to know how many learners are in the specified Barangays and Purok to determine the schedules of the intervention to be implemented. Profiling of the learners were made to know who among the respondents were having computers, laptops, tablets or even an android phone to be used in the intervention using Alfabasa Reading Program which is a play-based reading approach to enhanced the reading level of the kindergarten learners.

The lesson started with the introduction of the teacher using the alfabasa reading materials with their preferred gadgets available at home. Videos were distributed to parents for their usage at home. Monitoring tools were given to parents so they could make their assessment. While on the other hand, the teacher made their assessment to make ensure that the result could not manifest any biases of judgement.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in analyzing and explaining the data gathered.

For problems 1 and 2, the Frequency Count was used to measure the monthly progress of kindergarteners in terms of the video

clips/music and the provide checklist.

For problems 3 and 4, Mean and Deviation Standard Analysis were used to analyze the results of the monitoring tool conducted by parents in terms of reading materials and the over-all result of the Alfabasa monitoring tool.

For Problem 5, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test the significant difference between the monthly progress of the kindergarteners in Alfabasa Reading Program and the monitoring tool results.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analyses, results and interpretations of the data gathered in the study.

Problem 1: What are the pretest and posttest scores in the diagnostic test of the kindergarteners?

Table 1. *Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Kindergarteners in the Diagnostic Test*

Raw Scores	Performance Level	Pretest Scores		Posttest Scores	
		F	%	F	%
21-24	Outstanding	0	0.0	11	36.7
18-20	Very Satisfactory	0	0.0	16	53.3
15-17	Satisfactory	0	0.0	3	10.0
12-14	Fairly Satisfactory	0	0.0	0	0.0
0-11	Did not meet expectations	30	100.0	0	0.0
Total		30	100.0	30	100.0
Mean		2.13		19.70	
SD		2.06		1.86	

Table 1 presents the pretest and posttest scores distribution of the kindergarteners in the diagnostic test. As noted in the result, all of the respondents were having scores below 12 or belonged to did not meet expectations performance. In their posttest performance, nearly half (53%) of them were having very satisfactory performance, 37% of them belonged to outstanding performance and only 10% of them were classified as satisfactory performance. The mean score of their pretest and posttest were 2.13 and 19.70, respectively.

This manifested that most of the respondents showed a greater performance in their posttest scores. As gleaned from the table 1, there was really greater difference in their pretest scores from the posttest scores results. This only meant that the intervention was made to the learners though Alfabasa Reading Program with the help of the monitoring tool from parents and the teacher.

It was supported by Ucus (2015), that if one was engaged in any practical activity, involving physical work, all the senses were used to perceive knowledge through all the senses. Hence, the inflow of knowledge was through many channels and naturally was quick, complete, and accurate. This was learning by direct experience. It was an ideal method of making pupils acquires complete knowledge.

Problem 2: What are the Alfabasa monitoring tool results conducted by the parents?

Table 2 presents the Alfabasa monitoring tool results conducted by the parents. Result showed that all of the sampled kindergarteners were classified under did not meet expectations on their pretest scores but in opposite all of them have outstanding performance in their posttest scores.

Table 2. *Alfabasa Monitoring Tool Results Conducted by the Parents*

Raw Scores	Performance Level	Pretest Scores		Posttest Scores	
		F	%	F	%
29-33	Outstanding	0	0.0	30	100.0
25-28	Very Satisfactory	0	0.0	0	0.0
21-24	Satisfactory	0	0.0	0	0.0
17-20	Fairly Satisfactory	0	0.0	0	0.0
0-16	Did not meet expectations	30	100.0	0	0.0
Total		30	100.0	30	100.0
Mean		8.70		33.00	
SD		2.39		0.00	

This meant that the monitoring tool used by parents was helpful in attaining the better results for the respondents and that they were assessed based on how they perceived the learning of their children.

Problem 3: What are the Alfabasa monitoring tool results conducted by the teachers?

Table 3 presents the Alfabasa monitoring tool results conducted by the teachers. Result depicted that half of the sampled kindergarteners were classified under fairly satisfactory on their pretest scores and 46.7% of them belonged to did not meet expectations but in contrast all of them had outstanding performance in their posttest scores.

This result showed that the monitoring tool used by teachers to reveal the performance of the respondents showed that it was effective

because it was able to reveal the impressive performance results of the respondents in their posttest.

Table 3. *Alpabasa Monitoring Tool Results Conducted by the Teachers*

Raw Scores	Performance Level	Pretest Scores		Posttest Scores	
		F	%	F	%
29-33	Outstanding	0	0.0	30	100.0
25-28	Very Satisfactory	0	0.0	0	0.0
21-24	Satisfactory	1	3.3	0	0.0
17-20	Fairly Satisfactory	15	50.0	0	0.0
0-16	Did not meet expectations	14	46.7	0	0.0
Total		30	100.0	30	100.0
Mean		16.27		33.00	
SD		3.95		0.00	

Furthermore, one useful strategy to encourage learning a foreign language was using language games. When using games in the classroom, it was beneficial for teachers to have a complete understanding of the definitions of games, which usually were defined as a form of play concerning rules, competition, and an element of fun. Teachers should also consider the advantages of games: the ability to capture kindergarteners' attention; lower kindergarteners' stress; and give kindergarteners the chance for real communication (Ucus, 2015).

Hence, Dadheech (2018) cited that people have high expectations of everything digital; kindergarteners wished a variety of activities, rewards, surprises, and humor to stay up to their interest in learning. Finding new ways to grab the attention of learners and engaging them in the learning process was one of the main issues nowadays. Learning was not just rote memorization. Kindergarteners were able to gain any information and skills out of the dull learning process but they understand the application of skills and knowledge to solve real-life problems with help of an effective learning process. The knowledge and skills acquired through game-based learning were retained longer than information from other learning methods.

Problem 4: Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores in the diagnostic test of the kindergarteners?

Table 4. *Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores in the Diagnostic Test of the Kindergarteners*

Paired Variables	Diagnostic Test		t-value (df)	P-value	Remark
	Mean	SD			
Pretest	2.13	2.06	-38.264** (29)	0.000	Significant
Posttest	19.70	1.86			

Note: Analysis is based on Paired T-test **-significant at 0.01 level

Table 4 presents the difference between the pretest and posttest scores in the diagnostic test of the kindergarteners using the Paired T-test analysis. Result revealed that there was a high significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the kindergarteners in their diagnostic test ($t=-38.264, p=0.000$). This result suggested that the kindergarteners have better posttest performance ($M=19.70$) as compared to their pretest performance ($M=2.13$). Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores in the diagnostic test among the kindergarteners was rejected.

In addition, the result implied that the intervention made through the Alpabasa Reading Materials has greater effects on the reading performance of the respondents. Mihaela and Boghian (2014) stated that Game-based learning has been found to promote a positive attitude towards learning and develop memory skills, along with its potential to connect learners and help them build self-constructed learning.

Moreover, if one is involved in any practical task that requires physical labor, all of one's senses are used to perceive knowledge through all of one's senses. As a result, knowledge flowed in through a variety of avenues, and it was inherently speedy, complete, and precise. This was a hands-on approach to learning. It was an excellent strategy for ensuring that students learned everything they needed to know (Ucus, 2015).

Problem 5: Is there a significant difference between the monthly progress of the kindergarteners in Alpabasa reading program and the monitoring tool result conducted by parents based on their pretest assessment?

Table 5. *Difference on the Monthly Progress of the Kindergarteners between the Parents and teachers (Pretest Assessment)*

Group	Pretest Assessment		t-value (df)	P-value	Remark
	Mean	SD			
Parents	8.70	2.39	-8.977** (58)	0.000	Significant
Teachers	16.27	3.95			

Note: Analysis is based on Independent T-test **-significant at 0.01 level

Table 5 presents the difference on the monthly progress of the kindergarteners between the parents and teachers in their pretest

assessment. Result depicted that there is a high significant difference on the monthly progress of the kindergarteners between the parents and teachers ($t=-8.977$, $p=0.000$). This result showed that the teachers have better progress rating of the kindergarteners ($M=16.27$) as compared to the parents' progress report ($M=8.70$). Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference on the monthly progress of the kindergarteners between the parents and teachers was rejected.

This implied that, there was a remarkable difference on the result of pretest assessment as perceived by parents and the teacher which gave light to the conclusion that the parents might be too personal in giving a good assessment to their children since they were given a chance to monitor their progress. On the other hand, a perspective of teacher which is free from any personal judgments, she was able to rate the respondents based on how they present themselves objectively based on the monitoring tool.

Since the tool emphasized that there was no right or wrong answers, the monitoring tool made by parents and the kindergarten teacher was only be subjected to the domains where they were assessed.

Emergent literacy theory, which regards these endeavors as the earliest steps toward systematic reading and writing, validates children's attempts at language. There was a lot more to reading than just deciphering. The ability of a learner to discern in between words and pictures, together with their knowledge which were crucial skills to evaluate when deciding whether pupils can read and write (Mason & Sinha, 2008). As a result, both at school and at home, teachers must guarantee that students have the opportunity to read books and develop pre-writing skills. Another approach to education is constructivism, which believed that students should an active participant of learning.

According to Piaget (1962), children learn best when they were able to interact with peers and adults in their environment. Time to play, explore, experiment, and use language would be part of a constructivist educational approach. When it comes to teaching phonemic awareness and phonics, this technique was very legitimate. Children needed exposure to language and text as well as opportunity to explore and experiment with their use of language in order to grasp phonetic awareness, the alphabetic principle, and build phonics expertise. Constructivist theory and best practices for teaching phonemic and phonological awareness both agreed that children should use their "curiosity, inquisitiveness, and spontaneity to help themselves learn" (Morrow, 2008).

Problem 6: Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest monthly progress of the kindergarteners as conducted by parents?

Table 6. *Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Monthly Monitoring Progress as Conducted by the Parents*

Paired Variables	Monitoring Tools		t-value (df)	P-value	Remark
	Mean	SD			
Pretest	8.70	2.39	-55.580** (29)	0.000	Significant
Posttest	33.00	0.00			

Note: Analysis is based on Paired T-test

**-significant at 0.01 level

Table 6 presents the difference between the pretest and posttest monthly progress as conducted by the parents using the Paired T-test analysis. Result revealed that there was a high significant difference between the pretest and posttest monthly monitoring progress as conducted by the parents ($t=-55.580$, $p=0.000$). This result entailed that the kindergarteners had better post monitoring progress ($M=33.00$) as compared to their pretest monitoring performance ($M=8.70$). Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the pretest and posttest monthly progress of the kindergarteners as conducted by the parents was rejected.

This result implied that there was a remarkable difference recorded in the pretest and posttest result of the Monthly Monitoring Progress made by parent. As gleaned on the data presented, pretest and posttest assessment made my parents had a greater change from pretest to posttest which was intervened by the alpabasa reading materials.

As supported by Gagne et al. (2009) found that instructional materials can be used to help learners gain higher learning abilities through self-teaching or guided learning. This meant that the instructional materials primarily consist of "eliciting performance" and "offering feedback on performance correctness," as well as "providing learning guidance" for guided discovery learning.

In relation to the claim, if instructional materials were accepted as capable of having a significant impact on learners when used in a teaching lesson, it was reasonable to assume that their use would contribute to the expected teaching outputs.

Problem 7: Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest monthly progress of the kindergarteners as conducted by teachers?

Table 7. *Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Monthly Monitoring Progress as Conducted by the Teachers*

Paired Variables	Monitoring Tools		t-value (df)	P-value	Remark
	Mean	SD			
Pretest	16.27	3.95	-23.219** (29)	0.000	Significant
Posttest	33.00	0.00			

Note: Analysis is based on Paired T-test

**-significant at 0.01 level

Table 7 presents the difference between the pretest and posttest monthly progress as conducted by the teachers using the Paired T-test analysis. Result displayed that there was a high significant difference between the pretest and posttest monthly monitoring progress of the kindergarteners as conducted by the teachers ($t=-23.219$, $p=0.000$). This result revealed that the kindergarteners have better post monitoring progress performance ($M=33.00$) as compared to their pretest monitoring performance ($M=16.27$). Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between the pretest and posttest monthly progress of the kindergarteners as conducted by the teachers was rejected.

The null hypothesis was rejected because the pretest assessment using the Monitoring Progress as conducted by teacher showed a greater difference when the posttest assessment was conducted by the kindergarten teacher. This positively showed a better implementation of the alfabasa reading program as an intervention made by the reading teacher.

Hutchinson et al., (2014) backed up this claim, claiming that classroom teaching materials were the outcome of practical reason and purposeful invention. They were born out of observations and a desire to address the needs of pupils. Materials should be tailored to the needs and interests of the students for whom they were designed, as well as temper attitudes and preferences. If the main purpose of language education was to allow learners to become communicatively competent in the target language, which was English, new sorts of language teaching resources were required.

Furthermore, a material such as a module, according to Nunan (2011), allowed the student control over his learning. It was a collection of learning possibilities organized around a well-defined topic, with elements including instructions, stated objectives, teaching-learning activities, and evaluation using criteria-referenced measurement. In relation to the claim, if instructional resources were accepted as capable of having a significant impact on learners when used in a teaching lesson, it is reasonable to think that their use can contribute to the expected awareness of teaching and learning.

In addition, according to Denila (2018), the use of modern innovation provides a significant challenge to instructors, particularly for passive, underachievers, and students who are uncomfortable with the topic. A comfortable and enjoyable learning environment should be given for these sorts of students. They require a sense of achievement as well as a cycle of success that leads to emotions of self-worth. Even the best curriculum and ideal syllabus are useless unless they are accompanied by effective teaching practices. To make effective teaching it is important for the teachers to adopt and or develop effective teaching methods that suit the individual learning style.

Conclusions

Based on the finding, the following conclusions were set forth:

It was concluded that, the pretest and posttest scores in the diagnostic test of the kindergarteners had a remarkable results after the administration of the posttest diagnostic test.

It was concluded that the Alfabasa monitoring tool results conducted by the parents and the kindergarten teachers exemplified a pretest monitoring tool had a lower results while on the other hand the posttest monitoring tool showed a greater difference on its result. Thus, made the intervention of the alfabasa reading materials proven to be effective.

It was concluded that, there was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores in the diagnostic test of the kindergarteners so well as the the monthly progress of the kindergarteners which was both founded of great significance because of their striking results after the posttest administration.

In terms of the monthly progress of the kindergarteners as conducted by parents and as conducted by kindergarten teacher again showed a greater difference in the pretest and posttest administration. This only proved the intervention of the Alfabasa Reading Materials played a vital role in the remarkable results of both diagnostic tests and the monitoring tools conducted by both parents and teacher.

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are provided:

It is recommended for teachers to have innovate in teaching reading by using modified reading programs that will help learners improve their reading level.

The supervisors and school head could recommend a better ways to help teachers in the using different effective reading programs so that every learner is a reader.

It is recommended for future researcher to make a study on the development of new strategies in teaching reading.

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